
84. Gaia’s microlensing events

I INTRODUCED THE topic of gravitational microlensing in my earlier essay #11. Briefly, in general relativity, matter distorts spacetime, and the path of electromagnetic radiation is deflected as a result. If there is almost strict alignment between two stars along our line-of-sight, light rays from the more distant background object (the source) are bent by the gravity of the foreground object (the lens) to create images on Earth which are distorted (and possibly multiple), and which may be highly focused and hence significantly amplified.

Relative motion between source, lens and observer leads to brightness changes, over hours or days for stellar alignments, or even over years for quasars. At peak amplification, the brightness of a background star might increase by several magnitudes over a few days.

It is this *photometric* manifestation of microlensing which has been responsible for the many thousands of events that have been discovered to date. The *astrometric* effect, due to the associated tiny motion of the photocentre, is undetectable from the ground, but should (as I described in essay #11) be observable by Gaia.

Microlensing relies on the chance (and very rare) alignment of a background source, an intervening lens, and the observer. If the foreground lensing object is itself of complex structure (whether a cluster of galaxies, or a star orbited by one or more planets), then the background source may show a more complex light curve resulting from the time-varying magnification as the alignment changes. This phenomenon has led to the discovery of more than 350 exoplanets to date, almost all from the ground-based networks OGLE, MOA, and KMT.

THE EXPECTED DISCOVERY of many more photometric microlensing events has long been part of the scientific case for Gaia. And their prompt discovery and possible follow-up has long been part of the planning for the photometric ‘pipeline processing’. This demands careful calibration, comprehensive variability processing, and the rapid issuing of ‘science alerts’ for unusual and important ‘burst’ phenomena – including supernova and microlensing events (Hodgkin et al., 2021).

I described the goals and organisation of Gaia’s science alerts activity in essay #36. At that time (September 2021), nearly 50 microlensing events had been discovered as part of the alerts pipeline (some of which were also detected by OGLE), most in the Galactic plane (and in particular in its bulge) where source densities (and hence lensing cross-sections) are highest.

As of mid-2022, the science alerts task has reported more than 400 microlensing candidates, including unusual events such as Gaia16aye, a rotating binary lens (Wyrzykowski et al., 2020); Gaia18cbf, a very long duration event spanning 491 days (Kruszyńska et al., 2022); and Gaia19bld, a particularly bright event, $I = 9.05$ mag at its peak (Rybicki et al., 2022; Bachelet et al., 2022).

MICROLENSING EVENTS are, today, being discovered from the ground, not only by the dedicated search teams such as OGLE, MOA and KMT, but also serendipitously by other large-scale photometric surveys such as the All-Sky Automated Survey for Supernovae (ASAS), and the Zwicky Transient Facility (ZTF).

Gaia provides only relatively sparse and irregular sampling of its targets: thus, in the 34-month period covered by DR3, the average number of observations per source is about 40, with only some 20 in the bulge, but reaching some 100 at intermediate ecliptic latitudes.

But the Gaia observations also offer several important advantages: a high photometric accuracy; a wide range of magnitudes; its all-sky coverage; and its simultaneous 3-colour sampling (G , G_{BP} and G_{RP}).

In addition, the detailed astrometric and spectroscopic measurements which will be available with Gaia DR4, will be important ingredients for more complete microlensing solutions.

AS PART OF the Gaia Data Release 3 package, covering 34 months of data acquired between 2014–2017, the study and classification of the two billion objects with photometric time-series has been an important activity. The ‘variability processing unit’, CU7, has for example generated 1 840 947 142 associated light curves.

Within this, the systematic search for photometric microlensing events is described by Wyrzykowski et al. (2022). They worked with two samples: sample A based on an automated procedure and selection criteria tuned to the Gaia light curves; and sample B comprising specific events selected from the pre-existing literature.

For the former, the identification of rare microlensing events requires very efficient search techniques. In common with techniques developed for ground-based searches, their approach is to first identify all possibly variable stars exhibiting a single episode of brightening, and then study the narrowed-down sample in more detail with more computationally-expensive tests.

The first part ('Extractor'), used the G , G_{BP} , and G_{RP} data for a series of simple tests, in particular searching for a significant number of points brighter than the median; a brightening episode in all three pass-bands; and constancy of the light curve outside of the event. This resulted in 98 million sources for more detailed investigation. The second part, 'microlensing specific object studies', performed a microlensing model fit to the data.

Sample B consisted of 1527 suitable events already known from OGLE-IV. Two more were included from the ASAS-SN survey, and a further 7 had already been identified by the alerts system during the DR3 time interval.

THEIR FINAL COMPILATION comprises 163 events from sample A, and a further 233 events from sample B, with 33 in both, leading to a total of 363 Gaia microlensing events (designated GaiaDR3-ULENS-NNN). 90 were previously unknown, while 273 were independently identified by other surveys, notably ASAS and ZTF.

The majority of their events (228, or 63%) are located towards the Galactic bulge, with most concentrated at latitudes $|b| < 7^\circ$ (their Figure 2). The event density roughly follows the stellar density, and is concentrated towards the Galactic plane. The remainder are mostly concentrated to Galactic longitudes $|l| < 50^\circ$. Gaia EDR3 parallaxes gave source distances for 346 events.

Their estimated completeness ranges between 30% in the bulge to some 80% in the disk, and it is fairly complete for events longer than about 60 days. They consider that less than 1% are false events.

AMONGST THEIR discoveries: #001 is one of the events discovered in the DR3 data, but missed by previous surveys. #002 was previously classified as a long-period variable by the ATLAS survey. #007 was discovered independently by OGLE. #259 (Gaia17aqu) is one of the seven events flagged by the Gaia science alerts system. And #023 is a long-duration event discovered by the ASAS-SN survey in 2016.

Some splendid animations illustrating the lensing phenomena, with some real Gaia events, are given at the University of Warsaw [microlensing group's page](#).

Example Gaia microlensing events (Wyrzykowski et al., 2022; Figures 17–21). If the events were independently discovered (by OGLE, ASAS-SN, or Gaia Science Alerts) their alternative names are also given, and the plots include those data. For clarity, the key to the data points, and their model residuals, are not shown.